

Synthetic and Fungicidal Studies on Some 2-Arylidene-5-Phenyl-4H-Imidazo[2,1-b]-Thiazol-3-(2H)-ones and their Dibromo Products

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INTEREST in the synthesis of condensed thiazoles has been revived with the discovery of broad spectrum anthelmintic activity of tetramisole and related compounds¹⁻³. Synthesis of some new 2-arylidene-5-phenyl-4H-imidazo[2,1-b]thiazol-3-(2H)-ones and their dibromo products was undertaken with a view to study their antifungal activity as the introduction of bromine atom in the thiazole ring has recently been shown to enhance fungicidal activity^{4,5}. 2-Mercapto-4(5)-phenylimidazole (III) on treatment with ethylbromoacetate and various substituted aryl aldehydes in dry ethanol in presence of pyridine and piperidine gave the desired 2-arylidene-5-phenyl-4H-imidazo[2,1-b]thiazol-3-(2H)-ones (IV) which were brominated in chloroform to yield 2-bromo-2-(α -bromoarylmethyl)-5-phenyl-4H-imidazo[2,1-b]thiazol-3-(2H)-ones (X).

Compound (IV) was characterised by ir spectra. The product showed single spot on tlc, excluding the possibility of formation of 6-phenyl isomer. The fixation of phenyl group at 5-position in these compounds has been made on views expressed by Kochergin⁶, Pyl⁷ and Pujari *et al*⁸.

Experimental

The compounds were analysed for carbon and hydrogen on Coleman Analyser. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 377 infrared spectrophotometer in KBr phase. TLC was carried out on silica gel plates using absolute ethyl alcohol as eluent. All melting points were taken by open capillary method and are uncorrected.

Hexamethylene tetramine salt of ω -bromoacetophenone(I): It was obtained by the method of Long and Trautmann⁹. *ω -Aminoacetophenone Hydrochloride(II)* was obtained by known⁹ method.

2-Mercapto-4(5)-phenylimidazole(III): ω -Aminoacetophenone hydrochloride (5.98 g, 0.035 mole) and potassium thiocyanate (3.9 g, 0.035 mole) in 100 ml of glacial acetic acid were refluxed for 1/2 hr. Addition of water and thorough chilling resulted in the separation of a brown coloured solid melting at 252°. A sample was recrystallised from ethanol to a m.p. 260° (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 260-262°). The yield was 4.35 g (70%).

2-Benzylidene-5-phenyl-4H-Imidazo[2,1-b]thiazol-3-(2H)-one(IV_a), R=H: A mixture of the 2-mercapto-4(5)-phenylimidazole (1.76 g, 0.01 mole), ethylbromoacetate (1.67 g, 0.01 mole) and pyridine

(0.8 ml) in dry ethanol (20 ml) was heated on a steam bath for about 4 hrs. Benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 0.01 mole) and piperidine (0.7 ml) were added to the resulting solution and was further refluxed for 3 hrs. The reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice and water when a gummy product was obtained. It was extracted with benzene and on concentration a brown coloured compound was obtained. Recrystallisation from benzene gave light brown coloured needles, m.p. 125°, yield 2.5 g (80%). Found: C, 71.90; H, 4.20. C₁₈H₁₅ON₂S requires: C, 71.05; H, 3.94%. IR_{KBr} ν_{max} (cm⁻¹): 685, 760 (mono substituted benzene ring), 1470 (C-H deformations in CH₂), 1490 (C-N stretchings), 1600, 1625 (C=N), 1670 (C=O).

The relevant data regarding other 2-arylidene-5-phenyl-4H-imidazo[2,1-b]thiazol-3-(2H)-ones are listed in Table 1.

2-Bromo-2-(α -bromophenylmethyl)-5-phenyl-4H-imidazo-2,1-b]thiazol-3-(2H)-one (X_a), R=H: IV_a (1 g) in chloroform (30 ml) was treated with bromine (2 ml) in chloroform (30 ml) at 0-3° for 2 hrs. Removal of chloroform under reduced pressure at room temperature gave a vermilion coloured product. It gave a dibromo product (X_a) when treated with sulphurous acid and made alkaline with ammonium hydroxide. The product was purified by washing thoroughly with water and finally with ethanol.

The relevant data regarding 2-bromo-2-(α -bromoarylmethyl)-5-phenyl-4H-imidazo[2,1-b]thiazol-3-(2H)-ones are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—2-ARYLIDENE-5-PHENYL-4H-IMIDAZO-[2,1-b]THIAZOL-3-(2H)-ONES (IV)

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C
V	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	170(d)
VI	<i>p</i> -N(OH) ₂	150
VII	<i>p</i> -OH; <i>m</i> -OCH ₃	102
VIII	<i>p</i> -OH	92
IX	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	85

2-BROMO-2-(α -BROMOARYLMETHYL)-5-PHENYL-4H-IMIDAZO[2,1-b]THIAZOL-3-(2H)-ONES (X)

X _a	H	160(d)
XI	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	104
XII	<i>p</i> -N(OH) ₂	135
XIII	<i>p</i> -OH, <i>m</i> -OCH ₃	130
XIV	<i>p</i> -OH	118(d)
XV	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	176

Satisfactory elemental analysis for all the compounds were obtained.

Fungicidal activity: All the dibromo compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* by agar plate technique¹¹⁻¹³ at five different (500, 1000, 2000, 4000 and 8000 ppm) concentrations. All the compounds inhibited fungal growth even at 500 ppm of spray but complete inhibition was recorded at 4000 ppm only. The compound No. XII was found

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to inhibit the fungal growth completely even at 2000 ppm and is the most effective of the series.

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Synthesis of New Quinoline Derivatives as Antiamoebic Agents

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A large number of quinoline derivatives especially where the methyl or a methoxy substituent is at the '8' position are effective against microbial

diseases. Misra and Saxena¹⁻³ have reported some quinolines having a good activity against *E. histolytica* at a conc. of 125 µg/ml. Also, a group of anils have shown good activity against *E. coli*⁴⁻⁸. Recently, Misra and Agarwal⁹ have synthesised some substituted sulphazino quinolines and their anils which have shown considerable antiamoebic activity. The thiadiazoles, especially the thiadiazolyl urea¹⁰ and the 2-amino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole¹¹, have been reported to exhibit remarkable insecticidal properties.

These observations prompted us to synthesize some 2-aryl-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl-5-thio, 2-methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted quinolines and 2-aryl-amino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl-5-thio-4'-carboxymethyl, 2-methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted quinolines.

The compounds were single substances (tlc, benzenemethanol, 10 : 1). The thiadiazoles so prepared were characterised by their analytical and spectral data. Their ir (KBr) showed the presence of bands as follows : NH (3200), cyclic N=C=S (1470), cyclic N-N=C (1240), -S (1340) and C-Cl (820).

Experimental

4-Aryl thiosemicarbazides, 2-aryl-amino-5-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazoles, 2-methyl-6 or 7 or 8 aryl substituted 4-hydroxy quinolines and 2-methyl-6 or 7 or 8 aryl substituted 4-chloroquinolines were prepared as described in literature¹²⁻¹⁶.

2-Arylamino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl-5-thio, 2-methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted quinolines. I.: Sodium salts of 2-aryl-amino-5-mercapto-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole were prepared according to Sen Gupta *et al*¹⁷. The sodium salts were treated with substituted chloroquinolines (0.01 mole) in Na₂CO₃ solution (1.75 g in 10 ml water) and finally dimethyl formamide (10 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. It was cooled, diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with conc. HCl and the precipitate so obtained washed with water, dried and recrystallised from dilute methanol.

The quinoline derivatives thus prepared (45-50% yield) are described in Table 1.

2'-Methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted-4'-carboxychloromethyl quinolines. II.: The substituted hydroxyquinoline (0.01 mole) was treated with chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mole) in dry benzene and the mixture refluxed for 2-3 hrs. The contents were cooled, filtered and washed with ice-cold water. The compound (40-50% yield) was dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

Two such compounds were synthesised : a. 2'-methyl-4'-carboxychloromethyl quinoline, m.p. 215°, b. 2', 8'-dimethyl-4'-carboxychloromethyl quinoline, m.p. 217-218°.